

E-SATISFACTION AS A MEDIATOR BETWEEN INFORMATION QUALITY, SYSTEM QUALITY AND SERVICE QUALITY ON E-LOYALTY IN SAUDI ARABIA

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Abstract

The aim of the study is to explore the impact of website qualities measures (information quality, System quality and Service quality) on the E-satisfaction, and E-loyalty. Both quantitative and deductive approach are applied in this study based on a modified framework of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). Data were collected from 384 participants using Quota sampling with a self-directed survey, and results were derived based on the application of Partial Least Square - Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) approach. Based on previous studies there is seems a problem in the system, information as well as the service quality in Saudi Arabia in regards of internal navigation within a webpage; such as inconsistency in language interfaces, website layout, icon labelling, missing contact information, website updates, speed of the Website, clarity of Website, the effectiveness of the Website, easy navigation, and ease of use which can affect the service quality presented through the website, navigating in the website. Which determined serious problem with customers E-loyalty toward online shopping websites in Saudi Arabia. The results show all other hypotheses are accepted and showing a positive significant relationship. One hypothesis is rejected which is "There is a positive relationship between website service quality and consumer e-loyalty".

Keywords: E-commerce, Management, E-satisfaction, E-consumers, Technology

1. Introduction

The Saudi government is becoming more interested in developing e-Commerce systems to encourage national and regional businesses, mainly by creating a legal framework for online transactions (Alqahtani et al., 2019). Given the Kingdom's regional power, such a move would undoubtedly upset the Middle East's economic and trade infrastructure. However, there has been little research in developing countries on the factors determining e-commerce success (Al-Ayed, 2022). Furthermore, there have been few studies on the factors that explain the inequalities in e-commerce competency between developing and developed countries (Hatane et al., 2019; Reardon et al., 2021). Similarly, there is a dearth of published research on the variables influencing customer adoption and acceptability of e-commerce in Middle Eastern developing countries (Aimeur, 2021).

In the marketing discipline, building consumer trust is critical to the success of e-commerce businesses. One of the fundamental challenges merchants and buyers face in e-commerce is the question of trust (Alnassar & Aloud, 2021). Customer trust in e-commerce has become vital to the industry's long-term success. To enhance confidence, it is best to uncover components that impact trust. Trust is an influencing factor; it has been observed that most influencing factors in e-commerce have different reasons. This issue must be rectified (Ghali, 2021). The

website quality, on the other hand, has a significant impact on future customer intent. Consequently, the present research investigates the relationship between website quality, customer E-satisfaction, and consumer e-loyalty in an online shopping website. According to Jabeen and Hamid (2019), E-satisfaction and E-loyalty are essential for increasing customer engagement and retention. Web applications for Saudi e-business portals must be upgraded in design.

There has been little, if any, systematic research on website quality, customer happiness, and e-loyalty in the context of online purchases or shopping in Saudi Arabia (Baquee & Sevukan, 2019). Furthermore, most of today's research on online buying products has a clear emphasis rather than a conceptual focus that may be used to evaluate, predict, and influence online consumer behaviour. In this prominent research, gaps become the main objective of this study. Hence this study aims to empirically investigate the determinants of e-loyalty for e-commerce websites in Saudi Arabia by analyzing an integrated model for online shopping website attributes, customer E-satisfaction, and e-loyalty for e-commerce websites.

2. Literature Review & Hypothesis

2.1 Information quality and E-satisfaction

Ting et al. (2016) found that web designers view information quality as critical to website success. As a result, information, system, and service quality influence customers' willingness to remain loyal to the online service provider. Because, high customer satisfaction based on the amount of quality information directly influence customer loyalty (Al-dweeri et al., 2017). Recent researches (Mahadin, Akroush, & Bata, 2020; Manaf et al., 2018; Nasution et al., 2019) has found that the quality of information is a significant predictor of online consumers' trust, E-satisfaction with the e-goods, tailer, and, most importantly, purchase intent. Maintaining high levels of data quality reduces the cost of identifying and fixing insufficient data in online businesses' systems from a financial standpoint. E-commerce companies can also avoid operational mistakes and business process failures, resulting in higher operating costs and lower revenue.

- H1: There is a relationship between information quality and consumer E-satisfaction.

2.2 System quality and E-satisfaction

A web system, also known as a web-based information system, is an information system that uses Internet web technologies to provide data and services to users or other systems/applications, according to Manaf et al. (2018), It is a software system whose primary goal is to use hypertext-based concepts to publish and retain data. Ahmad, Rahman, and Khan, (2017) opined that systems quality has significant positive impact on e-satisfaction. Because, the system's high quality can create high security trusted website that can operate faster and keep all consumers' essential data safe. Also, most e-commerce systems strive to deliver high-quality services to end-users or customers, and to that end, they use various characteristics/attributes (such as Searching capabilities, flexible navigation, and personalization mechanisms) to satisfy specific end-user criteria. On the contrary, Dreheeb et

al. (2016) highlighted that it is acceptable to argue that e-commerce system quality and assessment methodologies will always depend on the system's capacity to fulfil end-user needs. During the development process, such quality issues should be considered.

- H2: A positive relationship exists between system quality and consumer E-satisfaction.

2.3 Service quality and E-satisfaction

Wilis and Nurwulandari's (2020) concluded that e-service quality has a favourable impact on E-satisfaction and e-loyalty. This suggests that the quality of e-services has an impact on Traveloka customers' E-satisfaction levels. According to Kaya et al. (2019), service quality is a metric for how well a service satisfies a client's or consumer's expectations. Hence, service firm operators routinely review clients' service quality to improve their service, quickly identify problems, and better gauge client E-satisfaction (Nasution et al., 2019). The willingness to provide high-quality services is crucial in the service business. Because service quality is critical to the survival and success of such companies, it is also a profitable survival strategy for them (Kaya et al., 2019). Here, the study anticipates that a high-quality website will increase customer E-satisfaction. This direction is consistent with previous research findings (Al-dweeri et al., 2017; Kaya et al., 2019; Pham et al., 2018):

- H3: A positive relationship exists between service quality and consumer E-satisfaction.

2.4 Information quality and E-loyalty

Buhalis et al. (2020) reiterated that information quality helps customers reach their objectives efficiently and facilitates customer requirements. And make it easier and faster to make online transactions. According to Wandoko et al. (2020), e-loyalty can be influenced by reputation and information quality. Their findings further show that e-loyalty is influenced by e-trust, information quality influences e-trust and e-loyalty, reputation affects e-trust and e-loyalty, information quality significantly impacts e-trust and e-loyalty, and e-WOM only has a significant impact on e-loyalty. The quality of information is a critical aspect for internet businesses. Consumers assess items and estimate their values based on the information offered by online merchants on their pages. Information quality may be used as a cue to represent the quality of the product/service. In addition, Hoang and Nguyen (2020) emphasized that Consumers rely on information, particularly visual information, displayed on an online shopper's website to judge its worth. Hence the information quality of their site is one of the essential components of their success.

- H4: There is a relationship between information quality and consumer e-loyalty.

2.5 System quality and the relationship with E-loyalty

Putri and Pujani's (2019) study on the impact of system quality on online loyalty among Shopee customers in Padang City reveal that system quality, information quality, e-service quality, and perceived value all had a favourable and substantial impact on online loyalty. From a quality standpoint, Zheng et al. (2013) concludes that information and system quality directly impact

perceived individual advantages and user E-satisfaction, which determines user intention to consume and contribute information in the future. Furthermore, their findings show significant quality problems in information exchange by modelling information quality and system quality as complex structures.

- H5: There is a relationship between system quality and consumer e-loyalty.

2.6 Service quality and E-loyalty

With a rapidly growing Internet user population (Jeon & Jeong, 2017), several studies have focused on the online medium's unique capabilities (websites service quality) that provide interactivity, personalized experiences, community, content, increased product selection, and information (Ting et al., 2016). Their findings reveal that online customers are loyal to businesses if their e-services always focus on improving customer's experiences such as digital application. Other studies (Li et al., 2015; Rita et al., 2019) show that the eTailQ scale and value perception help generate consumer loyalty and that both E-satisfaction and e-trust have shaped the e-loyalty development process. Moreover, Khan et al. (2019) findings suggest that the quality of e-services can increase e-loyalty among Pakistani e-customers. In the context of a developing economy, the study primarily examines e-commerce and focuses on e-service quality and its impact on e-loyalty.

- H6: There is a relationship between service quality and consumer e-loyalty.

2.7 E-satisfaction – E-Loyalty Relationships

Swaminathan, Anderson and Song (2018) emphasized that customer online shopping satisfaction has direct significant impact on e-loyalty. Thus, E-satisfaction is linked to e-loyalty because a variety of interpersonal and organizational factors influence the impact of E-satisfaction on loyalty. Wang et al. (2018) study examine the link between E-satisfaction and several forms of loyalty performance by combining empirical data from diverse literature domains. According to the findings, E-satisfaction significantly impacts attitudinal loyalty (e.g., trust, word-of-mouth, commitment), behavioral loyalty (e.g., repurchase intention, continuation intention), and composite loyalty.

- H7: There is a relationship between E-satisfaction and E-loyalty

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

2.8 E-SATISFACTION AS A MEDIATOR

As indicated by many studies (Ferreira et al., 2019; Mittal, 2016; Yadav et al., 2018), high quality information always positively impacts consumers' E-loyalty through consumers' E-satisfaction. On the other hand, Pandey (2016) has discussed in detail the positive impact of information quality on consumers' E-satisfaction. The result shows that the provision of adequate information directly improves customer experience, and this indirectly build a reboots consumers' e-loyalty. Through a mediating effect of e-banking E-satisfaction, Haq and Awan (2020) revealed that e-banking loyalty is boosted by dependability and website design, especially during COVID-19. The relationship between e-banking privacy and security and e-banking loyalty was shown to be mediated by e-banking E-satisfaction; however, the indirect influence of website design and dependability on e-banking loyalty was somewhat mediated. The findings of this study can aid policymakers in the strategic development of e-banking technologies and associated customer behavior. Kaya et al. (2019) instigated that e-service quality has a direct and indirect positive impact on e-loyalty through E-satisfaction. Indeed, the phenomenal growth of e-tailing has highlighted the importance of measuring and controlling e-service quality. As a result, it's critical to comprehend service quality in the e-commerce industry and what customers value in their online transactions;

- H8: There is a mediating effect of customer E-satisfaction between information quality and customer e-loyalty
- H9: There is a mediating effect of customer E-satisfaction between System quality and customer e-loyalty
- H10: There is a mediating effect of customer E-satisfaction between Service quality and customer e-loyalty

3. Methodology

Based on the scope of the study which focuses on the customers/online shopping in Saudi Arabia. The research procedure includes the application of original data from the self-directed survey. The current study takes an extensive scientific perspective; hence a, quantitative and deductive methods are used. This research provided a modified framework with seven variables and a sixteenth hypothesis that looked at the relationships between the variables. The proposed design has five constructs as antecedents: information quality, System quality, Service quality, Value Perception, and Atmospheric Website Cues; and two constructs as an outcome: E-loyalty and E-satisfaction. The population of this analysis is all adults (18 years and above) living in Saudi Arabia. The chosen adult population is because they can conduct an online shopping transaction. Based on different sources, the total population in KSA by December 2020 will be 34, 5 million (worldometers.info, 2020). Adults are 68.7% of the people, meaning they are 23.7 million.

The population is distributed into 13 administrative regions. Based on Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) formula of sample size calculation, the targeted sample size is 384 subjects that respect the minimum sample size for PLS analysis (90) and the effective size (166). The researcher collected more than the target sample size to secure a correct size after cleaning the data. For this particular study, non-probability sampling is chosen, and the techniques followed are quota sampling. The target sample size of 384 is chosen from the five main districts (the main city in every district) based on the population distribution. Therefore, a quota sample is the suitable data collection technique for this study. Five cities are chosen from the 13 main regions/ 5 main districts. The chosen process is judgmental based on the distribution and population size. Within social media platforms such as Twitter and Facebook, sampling is taking place from the available citizens. Data collection occurred during November 2020, December 2020, January 2021, and February-2021. For statically data analysis, the tools used in SmartPLS 3.

4. Results

In this study, different techniques were used, including manual visual and some statistical techniques, including engagement, univariate, and multivariate tests. For this study, the collected cases were 597, but the final valid data set was 384. The number of data after getting rid of the Uncompleted Cases Is 466, with a percentage of 78.06%. Initial Cases for Analysis been removed is about 60 with a percentage of 10%. The number of Unengaged Screening cases is 15. And the number of Univariate Screening is four cases, and finally, the number of Multivariate Screening is four cases. Based on that, the total Cleaned Cases for Analysis is 384, representing 64% of the total distributed cases.

Descriptive statistics showed a lot of variances in respondents' perceptions of variables. Items loading (Indicator reliability), Items internal consistency (reliability), Convergent validity, Discriminant validity, and Collinearity Assessment were all performed to ensure the dataset's reliability and validity (see Table 1 & 7 in ap

pendix). All the data displayed a high level of consistency. Based on Hair's rule of thumb, all the validity and reliability findings were sufficient (2016). The Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability reliability in this study are above 0.7, which also indicates high internal consistency. Therefore, the dataset is reliable. For Convergent Validity, all values are higher than the minimum threshold, which is a high level and widely acceptable, indicating that the dataset is free of convergent problems and suitable for further study.

Table .shows the quality criterion summary of the different constructs of the model :1

	AVE	Composite Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha
EL	0.647	0.880	0.818
ES	0.710	0.906	0.860
IQ	0.722	0.927	0.904
SQ	0.639	0.875	0.818
VQ	0.705	0.934	0.915

Table 2: Discriminant Validity Assessment of Research Variables

	EL	ES	IQ	SQ	VQ
EL	0.804				
ES	0.692	0.843			
IQ	(0.208)	(0.140)	0.850		
SQ	0.629	0.689	(0.033)	0.800	
VQ	0.800	0.818	(0.060)	0.674	0.840

The Fornell and Larcker criteria matrix is shown in Table 2. The matrix is a refined matrix of the correlations of the latent variable. The test is successful since the value in the diagonal is greater than any other number in the crossing column and raw. Table 3 reveals that the minimum VIF level between IQ and ES is 1.016, while the maximum VIF level between ES and EL is 1.435. As a result, all VIF values are within an acceptable range, and multicollinearity has been established (see Table 3).

Table 3: Multicollinearity Validity Assessment of Research Variables

	EL	ES
ES	1.435	
IQ	1.032	1.016
SQ	1.324	1.224
VQ	1.091	1.062

Table 4: Predictive Power and Predictive Relevance of Proposed Model

	Predictive Power		Predictive Relevance	
	R Square	Status	Q Square	Status
EL	0.580	moderate	0.365	large
ES	0.303	satisfactory	0.208	medium

According to the table 4, the key-dependent variable, effectiveness of loyalty (EL), has a moderate predictive power and a substantial predictive relevance. The linked R square is 0.580 (a power of 58.0%), while the corresponding Q square is 0.365 (a power of 36.5%). The prediction constructs related to the variable can explain more than 58.0% of the market effectiveness of loyalty (EL) variance. Results of the main dependent variable, E-satisfaction (ES), illustrate a satisfactory predictive power and a medium predictive relevance. The related R square value is 0.303 (a power of 30.3%), and the related Q square is 0.208 (a relevance of 20.8%). The prediction constructs related to the variable can explain more than 30.3% of E-satisfaction (ES) variance. One hypothesis is rejected: "There is a positive relationship between service quality and consumer e-loyalty." And all other hypotheses are accepted and show a significant positive relationship.

Table 5: Relation between independent and dependent constructs

Hypot he sis	Relation	Status	Sign	Path Coefficient	T Statistics	P-Value	Effective Size
H1	IO-> ES	Accepted	Positive	0.106	2.452	0.007	0.043
H2	SQ -> ES	Accepted	Positive	0.264	5.172	0.000	0.051
H3	VQ -> ES	Accepted	Positive	0.142	2.808	0.003	0.050
H4	IO -> EL	Accepted	Positive	0.098	2.752	0.003	0.036
H5	SO -> EL	Accepted	Positive	0.243	4.933	0.000	0.049
H6	VQ I -> EL	Rejected	Positive	0.243	0.341	0.366	0.042
H7	ES -> EL	Accepted	Positive	0.425	0.057	7.448	0.000

Table 6: The mediation impact of E-satisfaction on the Constructs

	Direct Effect			Indirect Effect			Total Effect		Status (Mediation)
	Path Coeff	P-Value	Status	Path Coeff	P-Value	Status	Path Coeff	P-Value	
IQ -> ES -> EL	0.099	0.003	Sig	0.048	0.014	Sig	0.146	0.000	Partial mediation
SQ -> ES -> EL	0.244	0.000	Sig	0.113	0.000	Sig	0.357	0.000	Partial mediation
VQ -> ES -> EL	0.018	0.366	Non-Sig	0.059	0.003	Sig	0.077	0.049	Full mediation

Table (Loading Proper) Items All for Assessment Loading Outer Indicator :7

	EL	ES	IQ	SQ	VQ
EL1	0.799458				
EL2	0.806309				
EL3	0.8001				
EL4	0.811853				
ES1		0.880865			
ES2		0.938516			
ES4		0.825436			
ES5		0.710566			
IQ1			0.76926		
IQ2			0.75312		
IQ3			0.822883		
IQ4			0.941266		
IQ5			0.94282		
SQ1				0.704576	
SQ2				0.775856	
SQ3				0.870555	

	EL	ES	IQ	SQ	VQ
SQ4				0.837702	
VQ1					0.785654
VQ2					0.756203
VQ3					0.901726
VQ4					0.86683
VQ5					0.821378
VQ7					0.896256

5. Discussion

The result in Table 5 shows that the relationship between information quality (IQ) and E-satisfaction (ES) is significant and positive as the (P-Value = 0.007) with a T statistics score of 2.452. On the other hand, the path coefficient for this relation is 0.106, and the small effective size score is 0.043. Based on that, and regarding the values viewed, the relationship is considered a significant and positive impact. The first mediation relationship states that E-satisfaction is a mediator between information quality and E-loyalty among customers of Saudi online shopping. After analysing the data, the researcher found that the direct impact shows that the p-value is 0.003 and the Path Coefficient is 0.099, indicating a significant effect. In contrast, the indirect effect shows that the p-value is 0.014 and the Path Coefficient is 0.048, indicating a significant effect. This relationship's total effect shows a p-value of 0.000, and the Path Coefficient is 0.146. Like other studies (Ha & Im, 2012; Kim et al., 2017).

This study demonstrates that online customers are more satisfied when they believe that their product information is high quality. E-loyalty seems to be influenced directly and indirectly via customer E-satisfaction by perceived information quality. There is a strong correlation between online consumers' perceptions of information quality and their likelihood of recommending a website. This is because information quality will ease and enhance the shopping experience, and the latter would generate positive E-satisfaction that ultimately leads to e-loyalty. Based on that, we can conclude that E-satisfaction's role as a mediator between information quality and E-satisfaction among customers of Saudi online shopping is significant, and there is a partial mediation relationship (see Table 6). This objective is supported and achieved by showing the impact of information quality on electronic loyalty, with electronic E-satisfaction considered a mediator for customers of online shopping in Saudi Arabia. Two out of the three relationships were supported and accepted.

The relationship between system quality (SQ) and loyalty (EL) is significant and positive as the (P-Value = 0.000) with a T statistics score of 4.933 (see Table 5). On the other hand, the path coefficient for this relation is 0.243, and the small effective size score is 0.049. Based on that, and regarding the values viewed, the relationship is considered a significant and positive

impact. The relationship between system quality (SQ) and E-satisfaction (ES) is significant and positive as the (P-Value = 0.000) with a T statistics score of 5.172 (see Table 5). On the other hand, the path coefficient for this relation is 0.264, and the small effective size score is 0.051. Based on that, and regarding the values viewed, the relationship is considered a significant and positive impact.

These results are in line with Dehghanpouri, Soltani, and Rostamzadeh (2020); Al-Dmour et al. (2019); Navimipour and Soltani (2016); Pradana et al. (2017). A higher level of customer E-satisfaction and e-loyalty resulting from improved system quality could lead to increased repeat business for this online shopping. Quality systems may thus be the greatest strategy to boost E-satisfaction and e-loyalty and increase sales by increasing the usage of quality systems. Consequently, it is advised that firms' managers and directors establish current IT infrastructure, create an efficient and user-friendly system, and improve electronic payment methods based on the experiences of top online enterprises.

The second mediation relationship states that E-satisfaction is a mediator between system quality and E-loyalty among customers of Saudi online shopping. After analysing the data, the researcher found that the direct impact shows that the p-value is 0.000 and the Path Coefficient is 0.244, indicating a significant effect. In contrast, the indirect effect shows that the p-value is 0.000 and the Path Coefficient is 0.113, indicating a significant effect. This relationship's total effect shows a p-value of 0.000, and the Path Coefficient is 0.357 (see Table 6). Based on that, we can conclude that E-satisfaction's role as a mediator between system quality and E-satisfaction among customers of Saudi online shopping is significant, and there is a partial mediation relationship.

These findings align with those (Kumar, & Lata, 2021; Hsu et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2019). The system's quality contributes to the smoothing and rewarding of the bricks-and-mortar purchasing experience and the development of client e-loyalty thru E-satisfaction. The ease with which online purchases are made and the essential needs for high-quality services are based on the system's efficacy. The system's quality facilitated customer-organization interactions, which was critical for e-commerce success. The system quality of a website is evaluated by the aggregated views of all its users about the site's accessibility, flexibility, and response time. Therefore, customers will have confidence in the system if it is available when required and answers swiftly to end-user queries. This objective is supported and achieved by showing the impact of system quality on electronic loyalty, with electronic E-satisfaction considered a mediator for customers of online shopping in Saudi Arabia. All relationships were supported and accepted. Table 5 indicates that the relationship between service quality (VQ) and e_loyalty (EL) is not significant and positive as the (P-Value = 0.366) with a T statistics score of 0.341. On the other hand, the path coefficient for this relation is 0.014, and the small effective size score is 0.042. Based on that, and regarding the values viewed, the relationship is considered a not significant relation and positive impact. This finding opposes research conducted by Ahmed, Al Asheq, Ahmed, Chowdhury, Sufi, and Mostofa (2022); Zhang, Jun, and Palacios (2021); Alkrajji and Ameen (2021); Slack and Singh (2020); Ahmed, Choudhury, Ahmed, Chowdhury and Al Asheq (2020); Boonlertvanich (2019); that revealed that service

quality and E-satisfaction have an impact on customer loyalty. Their results show that client service quality and E-satisfaction, directly and indirectly, influence loyalty. The impression of service quality has a greater overall effect on a customer's loyalty than their degree of E-satisfaction. Therefore, increasing client loyalty may be performed by expanding the scope and the quality of the service offered. The results also showed that E-satisfaction mediates the relationship between customer e-loyalty and service quality. This is in line with Alkrajji and Ameen (2021); Boonlertvanich (2019) and Annamdevula and Bellamkonda (2016). Improved service quality leads to higher customer E-satisfaction and - ultimately, more e-loyalty.

The relationship between service quality (VQ) and e_loyalty (EL) is not significant and positive as the (P-Value = 0.366) with a T statistics score of 0.341 (see Table 5). on the other hand, the path coefficient for this relation is 0.014, and the small effective size score is 0.042. Based on that, and regarding the values viewed, the relationship is considered a not significant relation and positive impact. The relationship between system quality (SQ) and E-satisfaction (ES) is significant and positive as the (P-Value = 0.000) with a T statistics score of 5.172. On the other hand, the path coefficient for this relation is 0.264, and the small effective size score is 0.051.

Third mediation relationship states that E-satisfaction is a mediator between service quality and E-loyalty among customers of Saudi online shopping. Based on that, and regarding the values viewed, the relationship is considered a significant and positive impact. After analyzing the data, the researcher found out that the direct impact shows that p-value is 0.366 and the Path Coefficient is 0.018, which indicated a non-significant effect. At the same time, the indirect effect shows that the p-value is 0.000 and the Path Coefficient is 0.113, indicating a significant effect. This relationship's total effect shows a p-value of 0.049, and the Path Coefficient is 0.077 (see Table 6). Based on that, we can conclude that E-satisfaction's role as a mediator between service quality and E-satisfaction among customers of Saudi online shopping is significant, and there is a full mediation relationship.

These results are consistent with prior studies (Kumar & Lata, 2021; Kuo et al., 2009; Yang et al., 2005; Manganari et al., 2011; Yadav & Mahara, 2017). The quality of the website influences the quality of the retrieved information. End consumers demand detailed information for their advantage. Consequently, websites should provide all necessary information, such as the company's history, a listing of available products, payment processes, and contact information for customer assistance. Consumers are frequently concerned about their safety while accessing any website. Customers are more inclined to refer firms with high-quality websites to their friends and family. Information, service, and system quality contribute significantly to consumers' E-satisfaction and e-loyalty. Due to the excellent quality of the website's service, satisfied users are more likely to return and become e-loyal (Manganari et al., 2011; Yadav & Mahara, 2017). While customers cannot directly assess the website's service quality, they depend on other indicators such as word-of-mouth recommendations or personal experience from individuals they trust to assist them in making their selection. Online shoppers are e-satisfied due to their prior experience and familiarity with online websites. This objective is supported. It has been achieved by showing the impact of service quality on electronic

loyalty, with electronic E-satisfaction considered a mediator for customers of online shopping in Saudi Arabia. Two out of the three relationships were supported and accepted.

6. Conclusion

This study provided insights into understanding the impact of (E-loyalty (EL), information quality (IQ), system quality (SQ), and service quality (VQ)) on the E-satisfaction (ES), and E-loyalty (EL). The current study is unique because it adds to the theoretical domain and gives consultants and practitioners fresh information. The results show that 70% and 85% of online female and men users in Saudi Arabia prefer to use international websites, which shows a high loyalty usage for foreign websites and low use for Saudi websites. There is a positive relationship between service quality and consumer e-loyalty, and the relationship between information quality (IQ) and E-satisfaction (ES) is significant and positive. Moreover, E-satisfaction has the most influence on e-loyalty, as an E-satisfaction can contribute too significantly on improving customers' e-loyalty. A followed by system quality which has the most significant influence on e-loyalty; therefore, organizations must improve the system's quality to improve loyalty.

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